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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

High-precision timing of an array of millisecond pulsars (MSPs) across the sky can permit the detection of low-frequency gravitational waves (GW) from supermassive black-hole binaries (SMBHBs) and potentially exotic sources such as cosmic strings, constrain dark matter and additional planets within the Solar System, and provide insight into the changing behaviour of the interstellar medium (ISM) on multiple timescales. Pulsar Timing Array (PTA) experiments are underway around the world, with Canadian institutions participating in the North American NANOGrav collaboration using the Arecibo, Green Bank, and JVLA telescopes. The CHIME/Pulsar collaboration has recently begun observing all visible NANOGrav MSPs on a daily basis, and will provide high-cadence monitoring of ISM dispersive and scattering changes to improve the precision timing attainable by NANOGrav. A detection of GW is expected within roughly the next decade.

This White Paper reviews the science attainable with PTAs, including current NANOGrav constraints on GW strains and the resulting implications for the SMBHB population and typical environments, and highlighting work on ISM variations, MSP astrometry and spins. Observing requirements, including the discovery of new MSPs, and strategy for future GW detection, are discussed in the context of current and planned telescopes and instrumentation, including the Square Kilometre Array.

Recommendations:

1. Canada should participate in the construction, operation, and data dissemination of the Square Kilometre Array at a level that allows Canadian scientists to take on leading roles with the pulsar-related Key Science Projects. Canadian expertise is well-established and our scientists should be given access to such leadership opportunities.
2. Funding should be found to allow the CHIME telescope, including its pulsar instrument, to operate beyond the nominal 5-year lifetime provided for by the initial CFI funds. CHIME/Pulsar has potential to be an extremely valuable addition to worldwide PTA efforts.
3. The Canadian community should find ways to support the existing Arecibo and Green Bank Observatories, through purchase of telescope time, through direct funding of on-site personnel, or through in-kind contributions in the form of instrumentation or software.
4. Funding should be sought to enable large-scale searches for new pulsars, especially MSPs, with telescopes such as CHORD and the SKA. This will require instrumentation (for CHORD at least), software and personnel.
5. If the U.S. component of the NANOGrav collaboration directs funding and effort toward the establishment of a large new telescope with dedicated observing time for PTA science, then a mechanism should be sought for Canadian astronomers to participate at a meaningful level. This could take the form of instrumentation, software or personnel contributions.

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1 Introduction

The radio-emitting highly magnetized neutron stars known as pulsars provide a unique opportunity to explore numerous aspects of fundamental physics and astrophysics. Lighthouse-like beams sweep across the Earth each time the pulsar rotates, allowing exact enumeration of "pulses" and thereby the determination of pulsar timing parameters to extremely high precision – spin periods can be measured in some cases to better than 1 part in 10^{15} (e.g. Reardon et al., 2016). The most stable pulsars are the "millisecond" pulsars (MSPs), which have been spun up by accretion of matter and angular momentum from an evolving companion stars. With timing precision of tens to hundreds of nanoseconds, MSPs allow constraints on, and soon perhaps detection of, low-frequency gravitational waves (GW) from binary supermassive black holes (SMBHs) at the centres of merging galaxies. Other potential sources of GW include cosmic strings and phase transitions in the early Universe. The observations used for GW detection can also be used to constrain fundamental physics (see companion WP E054) and could lead to the detection of low-mass objects such as clumps of dark matter crossing pulsar lines of sight. The properties of the ionized interstellar medium (density, magnetic field, turbulence) can be modeled based on MSP data.

Worldwide, some 100 MSPs are currently being timed for these purposes, mostly using large single-dish radio telescopes such as Arecibo, the Green Bank Telescope (GBT), Effelsberg, Parkes and recently FAST, but increasingly also with array telescopes such as the Jansky Very Large Array, the Westerbork Synthesis Radio Telescope, the Giant Metrewave Radio Telescope, and recently MeerKAT in South Africa and the Canadian Hydrogen Intensity Mapping Experiment (CHIME) telescope in Penticton, B.C. Observing, reducing data from, and carrying out the science derivable from these MSPs requires large collaborations. There are three well-established "Pulsar Timing Array" (PTA) collaborations: The North American Nanohertz Observatory for Gravitational Waves (NANOGrav), the European Pulsar Timing Array (EPTA), and the Parkes Pulsar Timing Array (PPTA) as well as emerging organizations in India and China. The International Pulsar Timing Array (IPTA) umbrella organization coordinates data sharing amongst the collaborations and encourages publication of combined data sets and results.

Canada has two long-established research groups with specialization in pulsar timing and in searches for new pulsars, as well as several other research groups with related interests such as pulsar VLBI and scintillometry, supernova remnants, and high-energy observations and theoretical studies of neutron stars and other compact objects. The two Canadian pulsar timing groups are members of NANOGrav and by extension the IPTA. They and other Canadian and US teams are also the developers of the dedicated pulsar instrument on the multi-purpose CHIME telescope. The CHIME/Pulsar team has established a data-sharing agreement with the NANOGrav collaboration; the CHIME telescope can observe the Northern NANOGrav MSPs on a daily basis and will allow for improvements in NANOGrav timing precision of 20–50%.

Canadian pulsar researchers have also been involved in science planning for the Square Kilometre Array (see companion WP E042) including participating in timing and search observations with the precursor MeerKAT telescope in South Africa.

This White Paper will summarize the science achievable with PTA observations and discuss observing requirements including the discovery of new MSPs, and strategy for future GW detection, in the context of current and planned telescopes and instrumentation. This discussion draws significantly on Science White Papers submitted by the NANOGrav collaboration to the US Astro2020 Decadal Survey in March 2019, notably by Cordes et al. (2019); Lynch et al. (2019); Taylor et al. (2019); Siemens et al. (2019) and Stinebring et al. (2019) along with the NANOGrav Project White Paper by Brazier et al. (2019).

2 Pulsar Observing and Timing

In order to reproduce as correctly as possible the signal emitted by a pulsar, modern instrumentation relies on the coherent dedispersion method (Hankins & Rickett, 1975). The dispersion measure (DM) is the column density of electrons between the observer and the pulsar. The DM induces a frequency-dependent delay in the pulsed signal, and in general varies over time due to the motions of the pulsar, Solar System and clouds through the ISM (e.g., Arzoumanian et al., 2018a). The coherent dedispersion technique relies on retaining full amplitude and phase information of the incoming radio signal, from which the phase filter of the ISM is then deconvolved. This

is a highly compute-intensive process, even with the data stream subdivided into channels of order 1 MHz, and therefore typically relies on GPU processors. This process can retrieve sharp profile features which enable high timing precision.

Along with causing variations in the DM, the changing ISM line of sight also results in changes to the scattering of pulsars. Multipath propagation through the ISM causes delays to portions of the pulsed signal, with the net effect of convolving the emitted signal with an exponential tail. Variations in this tail will bias the TOAs and affect the timing analysis (e.g. Ramachandran et al., 2006). At low observing frequencies, the effects of the variable ISM are especially pronounced, thus observations with the CHIME telescope, in particular, can be used to model these variations and produce estimates of the necessary corrections at the higher frequencies generally used at Arecibo and the GBT. Another promising avenue for even more precise corrections is cyclic spectroscopy of the incoming signal (Demorest, 2011).

Pulsar timing relies on the excellent reproducibility of the average pulse shape when integrating over thousands of pulses from a pulsar. A standard profile is formed using many hours' worth of data, and all observations are cross-correlated with this profile to produce pulse times of arrival (TOAs). With 100-m class telescopes, wide-bandwidth observations at about 1 GHz result in MSP TOA uncertainties of tens of ns in many cases. The TOAs are transformed to the Solar System Barycentre and then each pulse is enumerated to provide a coherent timing model. Parameters of the timing model include pulsar spin frequency and one or more derivatives, astrometry (position, proper motion and parallax), DM and variations, and orbital motion, if required. To enable GW detection, it is also necessary to identify and model various noise effects such as pulse jitter (e.g., Lam et al., 2019) and pulsar spin noise (e.g., Cordes & Downs, 1985). A timing model is judged by the properties of its residuals, defined as the difference between the measured TOAs and those predicted by the model. The best-timing pulsars have RMS residuals over decades of 100 ns or less (e.g., Zhu et al., 2015); an example including GBT and CHIME/Pulsar data is shown in Fig. 1.

3 Gravitational-wave Detection

An ensemble of MSPs can function as a pulsar timing array, with "arms" the size of the Galaxy and sensitivity to GW with frequencies close to $1/T$, where T is the length of the observing timespan. In practice, for decade-long observing projects, this implies sensitivity peaking between $\sim 10^{-9}$ and $\sim 10^{-8}$ Hz. The primary emitters of GW in this frequency range are expected to be binary SMBHs. These will form when galaxies merge and the individual central black holes spiral in toward the centre of the new merged galaxy (e.g. Jaffe & Backer, 2003). The gaseous and stellar environment in which an SMBH pair finds itself does influence its evolution, but the expectation is that GW radiation reaction will drive the orbital shrinkage once the pair is closer than $\sim 10^{-3}$ pc. Along with astrometric missions such as Gaia, PTAs are the only detectors that can observe the resulting gravitational radiation.

Binary SMBHs can produce 3 types of GWs that PTAs may be able to detect. An individual nearby binary will produce a coherent-wave signal in the timing data; current NANOGrav data places strong constraints on such a signal from within 120 Mpc (Aggarwal et al., 2019), but it is still possible that such sources may emerge above the background in future (Mingarelli et al., 2017). An inspiral of SMBHs can also produce a "memory" effect, which is a permanent change in the space-time metric (Favata, 2009). If such a step passes the Earth, all pulsars in the PTA would be seen to undergo an abrupt change in rotation frequency, with the amount depending on the relative orientation of the pulsar, the Earth and the source (e.g., Seto, 2009). Again, limits are derived from current data sets (Arzoumanian et al., 2015).

The form of GW emission most likely to be detected first by PTAs is the stochastic superposition of GW from many binary SMBH sources. Such a stochastic background is expected to have a strain h that follows a $f^{-2/3}$ power-law in detection frequency f . The amplitude of the strain at the reference frequency of 1 yr^{-1} is expected to be of the order 10^{-15} . Such an amplitude should be within reach of NANOGrav and international PTA projects within the next 5–10 years, depending on the number of pulsars in the array, observing cadence, etc. (Taylor et al., 2016). At the lowest frequencies, the exact form of the spectrum is still a matter of debate, with effects such as dynamical friction, stellar hardening, and interactions with a circumbinary disk potentially causing a turnover in

Figure 1: Timing residuals for the NANOGrav pulsar PSR J0645+5158. Light blue points are GBT data taken at a centre frequency of 820 MHz, orange are GBT data at 1500 MHz and dark blue are CHIME/Pulsar data taken at 600 MHz with 400 MHz of bandwidth. In the bottom panel, the CHIME/Pulsar data are shown on an expanded horizontal scale to demonstrate the high-cadence observing, with gaps indicating telescope shutdowns for software development. Residuals from multiple frequency subbands are shown for each epoch at each telescope.

the spectrum below about 10^{-8} Hz. Recent NANOGrav results place constraints on the binary SMBH population (Fig. 2) and also on a combination of environmental effects and initial binary eccentricities (Arzoumanian et al., 2018b). An eventual stochastic GW background detection will require demonstrating that the timing residuals from all possible pairs of pulsars follow a specific angular correlation function first described by Hellings & Downs (1983).

There are other potential sources of GW detectable by a PTA experiment, such as cosmic strings and superstrings, inflation, and phase transitions in the early universe. A detection of any of these sources would revolutionize our understanding of cosmology and fundamental physics. The NANOGrav 11-year constraint on cosmic string tension is $G\mu/c^2 < 5.3(2) \times 10^{-11}$, which is several orders of magnitude better than limits from cosmic microwave background (CMB) observations. While CMB experiments will have the best chance of detecting the lowest-frequency GW predicted by inflation, PTAs can constrain the spectrum of inflationary GWs and thereby some models of inflation. Phase transitions may have happened as the early universe expanded and cooled, possibly generating GW with wavelengths similar to the Hubble length at the time. The PTA-accessible wavelengths correspond to the time of the QCD phase transition, about 10^{-5} s after the Big Bang. A detection of any of these effects would need long timing baselines and a demonstration that the spectral characteristics are different from those of the stochastic GW background.

Merging stellar-mass binaries, for example in the Galactic centre or in globular clusters, could produce bursts with memory affecting the pulsars close to their lines of sight (e.g. Madison et al., 2017). PTAs would also be able to detect primordial black holes in the Galaxy, as these could accelerate pulsars or the Solar system (e.g., Seto & Cooray, 2007), or else affect pulse arrival times via lensing or Shapiro delay (e.g. Baghran et al., 2011).

Figure 2: The NANOGrav 11-year dataset 95% upper limits on the stochastic GW background (top) and corresponding energy density (bottom), with the straight black lines assuming a strain spectral index of $-2/3$ and the jagged black line representing independently determined free-spectrum components. The reduced sensitivity at $f = 1 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ is due to the need to fit astrometric parameters to the pulsar timing data. The dash-dotted line represents the expected slope for white noise. The coloured dashed lines and bands show the median and one-sigma GW background predictions for 3 different binary SMBH models: McWilliams et al. (2014) (green), Simon & Burke-Spolaor (2016) (orange) and Sesana et al. (2016) (blue). From Arzoumanian et al. (2018b).

Meanwhile, warm or "fuzzy" dark matter could cause oscillations of the gravitational potential of the Galaxy, which would be detectable as low-frequency GW; a constraint on the existence of ultralight bosons can be found in Porayko et al. (2018).

4 Tests of Gravitational Theories with PTAs

Gravitational waves detected by PTAs can be compared with the expectations of general relativity (GR). In particular, GR predicts that GW will have two polarizations, while some alternate theories predict as many as 6 polarizations (e.g. Eardley et al., 1973). PTAs can investigate this possibility by recognizing that the line of sight to each pulsar corresponds to a particular projection of the set of GW polarizations, and so linear combinations of these data can offer multiple constraints on the possible extra polarizations. Initial limits have already been set using the NANOGrav 9-year data release (Cornish et al., 2018).

5 Velocities, Interstellar Medium and More

Apart from the combination of data from multiple pulsars for GW purposes, the simple act of timing MSPs for a decade or more yields a wealth of information about the individual pulsars or binary systems. The measurement and implications of pulsar masses are discussed in companion WP E054, so here we focus on other science. The

long timing baselines in PTA data sets allow for the measurement of many pulsar proper motions and in several cases also parallaxes (e.g. Matthews et al., 2016). This leads to an understanding of at least a component of pulsar velocities and allows for population modeling, provides signposts toward extraordinary binaries (Kaplan et al., 2016), and related topics.

While dispersion and scattering, and especially variations in these phenomena, represent systematics to be overcome in obtaining the highest precision pulsar timing data, they are in fact also a window onto the properties of the turbulent ISM on a wide range of length scales. An example is the appearance in PTA data of two abrupt decreases in the dispersion measure toward PSR J1713+0747 in 2008 and 2016, lasting 100-200 days and possibly due to lensing by a structure in the ISM (Lam et al., 2018). More "classically," the DM variations, often with annual structure, in multiple pulsars in the NANOGrav data set have been investigated on AU scales and modeled based on the known motions of the Earth and the pulsar (Jones et al., 2017). Variations on timescales as short as weeks were found.

6 Science Requirements

Effective PTA science requires large telescopes, long observation baselines, high cadence observing, wide observing bandwidths, and a steady influx of new suitable MSPs. Here we briefly justify each of these requirements and explore possibilities going forward, while noting that community work on better calibration, ISM mitigation, and radio-frequency interference excision algorithms, along with improved Solar System ephemerides, will also be needed.

Large Telescopes: Radiometer noise (as opposed to, e.g., pulse jitter) is still the limiting factor for the timing precision in most MSPs observations (Arzoumanian et al., 2018a). Pulse TOA precision scales directly with the collecting area of the telescope, making the use of large telescopes essential. While Arecibo and the GBT have avoided shutdown threats for the immediate future, there is still a possibility of closure within the next decade, and meanwhile both telescopes are increasingly looking to purchases of observing time to make up for reduced operations budgets. The US component of the NANOGrav collaboration has been able to purchase some time through an NSF Physics Frontier Center grant, but that is currently up for renewal. The collaboration is actively discussing ideas for participation in future telescopes such as the DSA-2000 and the Next Generation Very Large Array (Brazier et al., 2019). It is essential that Canadian astronomers participate in NANOGrav's future large-telescope plans, especially if there is a dedication of time to PTA observing. The new FAST telescope in China is accessible to foreign observers via collaboration with local astronomers, but it is unlikely to provide a high enough cadence on MSPs in the near future. While MeerKAT is providing some excellent early results, the leadership of the PTA-related timing project rests with an Australian group, and the TOAs are likely to go directly to the IPTA. Moreover, the many excellent MSPs in the North are largely inaccessible to MeerKAT. CHIME/Pulsar provides superb monitoring of the Northern MSPs and the operation of this telescope needs to be funded for as long as possible. Notably, the SKA has tremendous promise for PTA science, with Phase I likely to make a GW detection if that has not already been accomplished, and Phase II (or possibly even Phase I) allowing the exploration of the GW spectrum (Janssen et al., 2015). There is excellent potential for Canadian leadership within this important SKA Key Science Project. A crucial point is that it is essential to have overlap with existing telescopes when new telescopes are brought on line (similarly for new instrumentation at existing telescopes) in order to determine timing offsets between data sets at the sub-100 ns level.

Long observing Baselines: For an observing timespan T , the GW signals from a stochastic background and from bursts with memory increase as $T^{5/3}$ and T , respectively. Current values of T are close to the orbital periods of Jupiter and Saturn; with even longer baselines it will be possible to eliminate covariances of these planets' effects on the Solar System ephemeris, further improving the GW sensitivity. Long-term support of a PTA program is essential.

High Cadence Observing: Daily to weekly observing makes it significantly easier to develop models of ISM variability and thereby generate corrected, high-precision TOAs. Astrometric parameters also become easier to determine to high precision. Here the CHIME/Pulsar experiment is a clear winner, with the ability to monitor

Northern NANOGrav MSPs on a daily basis. Future surveys (see below) are likely to discover thousands of new pulsars. In some cases, scientifically valuable systems, such as ultra-compact binaries, will be easy to identify, but finding the "diamonds in the rough", such as massive neutron stars, will require more detailed follow-up. Another exciting possibility is a pulsar-black hole binary. Such a system could be indistinguishable from a more typical isolated pulsar without long-term monitoring to reveal its binary nature and the relativistic effects that will identify the companion. It will therefore be critical to monitor all new pulsars for at least weeks to months with sensitive telescopes. Wide-field instruments like CHIME excel in this regard.

Wide Observing Bandwidths: With the pulse TOA precision dependent in part on observing bandwidth, large fractional observing bandwidths are clearly a necessity. These also aid the development of ISM variability models. There are currently "ultra-wide-band" receivers under development for the GBT and Arecibo; these will allow the effective doubling of integration time per pulsar, as currently each epoch involves observations at two separate central frequencies. Instrumentation on future telescopes needs to follow this philosophy. While there is usually significant pulse profile evolution across wide bands, algorithms to address this fact when deriving TOAs are being actively developed (e.g., Pennucci et al., 2014)

New MSPs: As demonstrated in Taylor et al. (2016), adding new MSPs to an existing PTA reduces the time to detection and will moreover help to identify GW even in the presence of environmental coupling and possible stalling. It is not sufficient to time just the few best MSPs; such a strategy will permit excellent upper limits on a GW background, but will not provide the large number of pulsar pairs needed to check for the expected quadrupolar angular correlation signal. A nominal international goal is 200 suitable MSPs spread across the full sky. Therefore searching for new pulsars is an essential adjunct program to PTA observations. The "PALFA" multibeam Galactic-Plane pulsar search program at Arecibo is Canadian-led, and Canadian groups participate in an all-sky survey with the GBT. Funding has been obtained for a pulsar search with the CHIME telescope; however, as this will use the Fast Radio Burst data stream with 1-ms sampling, it will be best suited finding slow pulsars and not candidates for PTA inclusion. More promising is the proposal to build the Canadian Hydrogen Observatory and Radio-transient Detector (CHORD; see WP E029), which has the potential to increase the number of MSPs by roughly an order of magnitude (see also complementary WP E054). In the South, MeerKAT and eventually the SKA will also find large numbers of suitable pulsars (Keane et al., 2015).

7 Recommendations

Based on the science opportunities described in Sections 3, 4, and 5, the requirements in Section 6, and Canadian ambitions, we make the following recommendations:

1. Canada should participate in the construction, operation, and data dissemination of the Square Kilometre Array at a level that allows Canadian scientists to take on leading roles with the pulsar-related Key Science Projects. Canadian expertise is well-established and our scientists should be given access to such leadership opportunities.
2. Funding should be found to allow the CHIME telescope, including its pulsar instrument, to operate beyond the nominal 5-year lifetime provided for by the initial CFI funds. CHIME/Pulsar has potential to be an extremely valuable addition to worldwide PTA efforts.
3. The Canadian community should find ways to support the existing Arecibo and Green Bank Observatories, through purchase of telescope time, through direct funding of on-site personnel, or through in-kind contributions in the form of instrumentation or software.
4. Funding should be sought to enable large-scale searches for new pulsars, especially MSPs, with telescopes such as CHORD and the SKA. This will require instrumentation (for CHORD at least), software and personnel.
5. If the U.S. component of the NANOGrav collaboration directs funding and effort toward the establishment of a large new telescope with dedicated observing time for PTA science, then a mechanism should be sought for Canadian astronomers to participate at a meaningful level. This could take the form of instrumentation, software or personnel contributions.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

The detection of low-frequency gravitational waves from supermassive black-hole binaries would be a tremendous advance to gravitational-wave science, complementary to what can be achieved with ground- and space-based interferometers. The detection will vastly increase our understanding of the population and dynamics of supermassive black holes. Any detection of GW from other sources, such as cosmic strings, or observation of excess polarizations of GW would revolutionize our understanding of cosmology and gravity, respectively.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

Physical challenges to the detection of GW include human-generated interference, interstellar medium variations including dispersion and scattering, calibration including polarization leakage, and the evolution of pulse profile shapes over wide observing bands. All of these topics are currently under study for mitigation techniques, and we expect algorithm improvements to continue with further work. It is also important to maintain the radio-quiet zone around the Dominion Radio Astrophysical Observatory in Penticton as well as worldwide radio-quiet zones.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canadian pulsar groups are already recognized as being world leaders, with expertise in pulsar searches, timing, instrumentation and planning. This will certainly continue through the eras of NANOGrav, CHIME, CHORD, and, with suitable funding levels, the SKA.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Yes; in fact Canadian and US community members are authors of this document. Canada's contributions to pulsar planning with the international SKA community are also well-recognized.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Pulsar Timing Array projects are by definition long-term, with increasing scientific return as the timespan of observations grows longer. This field may be expected to be fruitful well beyond the next decade.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Each of the recommendations listed above provides Canadian astronomers with the opportunity to participate in the most cutting-edge pulsar science, sometimes by making small-scale but vital contributions to large projects and sometimes (CHIME, CHORD) by leading the projects. There is a well-balanced mix of contribution levels in the recommendations which will allow effective work and leadership by Canadians.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The reduced NSF funding to Arecibo and the GBT is an immediate threat to the NANOGrav program. Both telescopes could still be at risk for closure within the next decade, and at best there will be greatly reduced open-skies time to compensate for reduced NSF support. Canadian members will work with their US counterparts to argue for maintenance of open-skies time and to provide strong funding requests for purchased time. Large new projects such as CHORD and the SKA are often subject to schedule slippage, but given ongoing observations with existing facilities, this represents more a delay in achieving science goals rather than a show-stopper.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

HQP associated with PTA projects are trained in time-series analysis and modeling techniques and always develop strong computational skills and the ability to deal with large data volumes; such skills are highly sought-after in the commercial sector. The CHIME telescope has brought about a collaboration between cosmologists and pulsar/FRB astronomers which is relatively interdisciplinary. The NANOGrav collaboration has a long-standing commitment to EDI, with a formal Diversity Plan and an Equity Committee which has had continuous Canadian representation. NANOGrav also has a strong Education and Public Outreach working group, and the various CHIME teams have done significant public outreach. We can expect continued PTA activity to draw interest at all levels, from the general public to new HQP.

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